

G1. Interact @RASOP: Traceability project. Part 2.

Name: _____ email: _____

Session instructions:

This workshop consists of one task: **Discovering the traceability links between a set of user stories and an EDG using OntoTrace**. Since this is a graded workshop (**3% of the final grade**), you must develop it individually! **Talking, chatting, and sending emails are not allowed during the workshop**. Read first all the instructions before to start.

Follow the next steps to complete the workshop:

- 1) Access to Moodle's activity titled: "Traceability project part 2."
- 2) Download the files: Traceability-project-part2.drawio, EDG.png, and UserStories.pdf.
- 3) Open the file "Traceability-project-part2.drawio" using the draw.io application in windows or using your browser in "diagrams.net".
- 4) Please write down now your starting time

Starting time (HH:MM): _____

- 5) Open Onto Trace and discover all the traces between the user stories and the EDG. You can use the files Traceability-project-part2.drawio, EDG.png, and UserStories.pdf to review which user stories and EDG elements are part of the case.

Remember, the important thing about this workshop is **NOT** that **ALL** the artifacts have a trace link, but you be **ACCURATE** on the trace links you discover. Please let the lecturers know if you have any problems, questions, or comments during the workshop!

- 6) When you think there are no more trace links between user stories and the EDG to discover, take and save a screenshot of your final solution done in OntoTrace. Then, write down your ending time:

Ending time (HH:MM): _____

- 7) Upload the screenshot take from OntoTrace via Moodle.

8) Fill in the following questionnaire:

G1	How much do you agree with the following statements? Mark with an X your agreement level, having: (1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree; (3) Nor disagree nor agree, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree					
	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
	Using OntoTrace , I easily traced user stories into the EDG.					
	Tracing user stories into the EDG is an understandable process using OntoTrace .					
	I found that the OntoTrace generally helps trace user stories into the EDG.					
	It seemed to me that tracing user stories into the EDG using OntoTrace is a straightforward process.					
	I am sure that I have the needed abilities to trace user stories into the EDG.					
	I think the effort to trace the user stories to the EDG using OntoTrace is low.					
	In general, it is easy to understand how to trace user stories to EDG by using OntoTrace .					
	I could explain how to trace user stories into the EDG to another person that does not know OntoTrace .					
	Using OntoTrace , I think it is easy to trace user stories into the EDG					
	I think OntoTrace is an effective solution for tracing user stories into EDG.					
	I can efficiently trace user stories into the EDG by using OntoTrace .					
	I think using OntoTrace for tracing user stories into EDG is the best way to do it.					
	Definitely, I will use OntoTrace for tracing user stories into the EDG.					
	I prefer to use OntoTrace for tracing user stories into the EDG.					

9) When you finish uploading the screenshot, and have filled the questionnaire, deliver the documents to one of the lecturers, they will check if everything is OK.

G2. Interact @RASOP: Traceability project. Part 2.

Name: _____ email: _____

Session instructions:

This workshop consists of one task: **Discovering the traceability links between a set of user stories and an EDG using OntoTrace**. Since this is a graded workshop (**3% of the final grade**), you must develop it individually! **Talking, chatting, and sending emails are not allowed during the workshop**. Read first all the instructions before to start.

Follow the next steps to complete the workshop:

- 1) Access to Moodle's activity titled: "Traceability project part 2."
- 2) Download the files: Traceability-project-part2.drawio, EDG.png, and UserStories.pdf.
- 3) Open the file "Traceability-project-part2.drawio" using the draw.io application in windows or using your browser in "diagrams.net".
- 4) Please write down now your starting time

Starting time (HH:MM): _____

- 5) Open Onto Trace and discover all the traces between the user stories and the EDG. You can use the files Traceability-project-part2.drawio, EDG.png, and UserStories.pdf to review which user stories and EDG elements are part of the case.

Remember, the important thing about this workshop is **NOT** that **ALL** the artifacts have a trace link, but you be **ACCURATE** on the trace links you discover. Please let the lecturers know if you have any problems, questions, or comments during the workshop!

- 6) When you think there are no more trace links between user stories and the EDG to discover, take and save a screenshot of your final solution done in OntoTrace. Then, write down your ending time:

Ending time (HH:MM): _____

- 7) Upload the screenshot take from OntoTrace via Moodle.

8) Fill in the following questionnaire:

G2	How much do you agree with the following statements? Mark with an X your agreement level, having: (1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree; (3) Nor disagree nor agree, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree					
	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
	Using OntoTrace , I easily traced user stories into the EDG.					
	Tracing user stories into the EDG is an understandable process using OntoTrace .					
	I found that the OntoTrace generally helps trace user stories into the EDG.					
	It seemed to me that tracing user stories into the EDG using OntoTrace is a straightforward process.					
	I am sure that I have the needed abilities to trace user stories into the EDG.					
	I think the effort to trace the user stories to the EDG using OntoTrace is low.					
	In general, it is easy to understand how to trace user stories to EDG by using OntoTrace .					
	I could explain how to trace user stories into the EDG to another person that does not know OntoTrace .					
	Using OntoTrace , I think it is easy to trace user stories into the EDG					
	I think OntoTrace is an effective solution for tracing user stories into EDG.					
	I can efficiently trace user stories into the EDG by using OntoTrace .					
	I think using OntoTrace for tracing user stories into EDG is the best way to do it.					
	Definitely, I will use OntoTrace for tracing user stories into the EDG.					
	I prefer to use OntoTrace for tracing user stories into the EDG.					

9) When you finish uploading the screenshot, and have filled the questionnaire, deliver the documents to one of the lecturers, they will check if everything is OK.